

Elements removed by brown rice grain were compared with the concentrations removed by hulls and straw and the resulting nutrient harvest index (Table 2). In an average 10 t/ha crop of Amaro at 14% moisture, brown grain removed 103 kg N; straw, 61 kg N; and hulls, 3.7 kg N. Brown rice removed most of the P (25 kg in an average 10 t/ha rice crop), while straw removed 4.8 kg and hulls removed 0.4 kg, giving a nutrient harvest index of 83%. The amounts of K, Mg, Ca, Zn, and Mo removed by straw exceeded those removed by brown rice; hulls contained low concentrations. The proportion of Mn, Fe, Na, and Al removed by grain was lower than or equal to that removed by hulls, with straw removing the greatest proportion. Straw and grain removed similar amounts of Cu and S, with much lower concentrations in hulls.

At the rice mill, hulls are separated from the grain, and most are dumped and burned or converted to livestock feed. Rice straw is usually burned after harvest.

N, P, and S are the dominant fertilizer inputs for rice in southern NSW. Incorporating residues would enhance the recycling rate of all the nutrients studied. However, P would be supplied in relatively small amounts because it is predominantly exported in the brown grain. ■

Table 2. Partitioning of mineral elements by an average Amaro rice crop yielding 10 t/ha (at 14% moisture).^a

Element	Element removed			Total nutrients removed	Nutrient harvest index (%) ^b
	In brown grain	In hulls	In straw		
			(kg/ha)		
Nitrogen	103	3.7	61	167.7	61
Phosphorus	25	0.4	4.8	30.2	83
Potassium	21	9.0	212	242.0	9
Magnesium	10	0.6	14	24.6	41
Sulfur	8	0.4	5.8	14.2	56
Calcium	0.9	1.4	23	25.3	4
Manganese	0.4	0.6	5.8	6.8	6
Sodium	0.2	0.3	27	27.5	1
Aluminum	0.1	0.1	6.2	6.4	2
Iron	0.1	0.1	2.2	2.4	4
			(g/ha)		
Zinc	140	26	259	425	33
Copper	35	2	35	72	49
Molybdenum	6.0	1.4	25	32.4	19

^aA rice crop yielding 10 t/ha (at 14% moisture) will have an average of 8.4 t grain/ha, 1.6 t hulls/ha, and 11 t straw/ha. The data were calculated using concentrations of minerals on an oven-dry weight basis and multiplying by 7.5, for grain, 1.4 for hulls, and 9.6 for straw (i.e., yields at 0% moisture).

^b Nutrient harvest index = $100 \times \frac{\text{Amount in grain}}{\text{Amount in grain, hulls, and straw}}$

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Fertilizer management

Effects of *Sesbania rostrata* population, time of harvest, and urea application rate on lowland rice production

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We studied the effects of plant population and time of harvest of *Sesbania rostrata* and urea application rate on lowland rice production.

Soil was silty clay with a pH of 5.7, 0.16% N, 2.34% organic C, 16.76% ppm P, C-N ratio of 14.62, and 0.48 meq K/100 g.

The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications during 1991-92 wet season (Oct-Mar). The main plot treatment was *S. rostrata* population at two levels: 62,500 and 125,000 plants/ha. *S. rostrata* harvest time was the treatment in the subplot (45 and 60 days after sowing [DAS]),

Table 1. Effect of plant population and time of harvest on N concentration (%) in plant tissue of *S. rostrata*. Maros, Indonesia.

Time of harvest (DAS)	Plant population/ha ^a	
	62,500	125,000
45	2.45 a	1.88 b
60	1.47 c	1.86 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by DMRT.

and levels of urea application (0, 23, and 46 kg N/ha) were the sub-subplot treatments.

S. rostrata seeds were sown in the plot and thinned based on the plant population treatment. *S. rostrata* was plowed under in preparation for rice planting according to the treatments. Rice cultivar Cisadane was planted a week later. Half of the urea was applied at planting and the rest at panicle initiation. All of the plots were also treated at planting with triple superphosphate at 26.4 kg P/ha and KCl at 41.5 kg K/ha.

Table 2. Effect of *S. rostrata* plant population, time of harvest, and rate of urea application on rice panicle number, unfilled grains, and grain yield. Maros, Indonesia.

Treatment	Panicles/hill (no.)	Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>S. rostrata</i> population/ha			
62,500	122.47 a	15.95 a	5.3 a
125,000	128.61 a	14.47 a	5.6 a
Time of harvest of <i>S. rostrata</i> (DAS)			
45	128.70 a	14.56 a	5.4 a
60	122.38 a	15.86 a	5.5 a
Rate of urea application (kg N/ha)			
0	115.32 b	17.08 a	4.4 c
23	126.62 a	15.49 b	5.7 b
46	134.68 a	13.06 c	6.4 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by DMRT.

The greatest N content in *S. rostrata* plant tissue occurred with 62,500 plants/ha and harvest at 45 DAS (Table 1).

The plant population, time of *S. rostrata* harvest, and their interaction were not significant. The rate of urea application, however, was significant.

The rice crop responded to urea application. *S. rostrata* green manure gave the same rice yield as did 46 kg N/ha as urea. Applying urea at 46 kg N/ha could

decrease the unfilled grains/panicle, increase the panicle/hill, and increase grain yield (Table 2). ■

Fertilizer management—**inorganic sources**

Band placement of urea solution increases N use efficiency in transplanted lowland rice

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Most of the N fertilizer used in rice in Asia is urea. Rice under flooded systems makes poor use of urea because of losses through ammonia volatilization, denitrification, leaching, immobilization, and ammonium fixation. Scientists at IIRI modified a technique where urea solution is placed in bands using a two-row, push-type applicator for transplanted lowland rice. Nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) and rice yield were significantly increased using this technique compared

with point placement of urea supergranules (USG).

We evaluated the IIRI applicator for urea solution (see figure) with broadcast prilled urea (PU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and point placement of USG at Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Aliyar Nagar, Tamil Nadu, during 1992-93, followed by on-farm testing. The experiments were laid out in randomized complete block design with 11 treatments and three replications using varieties IR50 and ADT36.

All growth and yield parameters increased significantly (see table) with band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits compared with applying 100 kg N/ha as PU in a conventional 3-way split. The grain yield increase with band placement was 10% more for IR50 and 25% more for ADT36 than that

Urea solution applicator.

with the 3-way PU split. Higher agronomic efficiency and apparent recovery of N were obtained with band placement (see table) of urea solution. At 100 kg N/ha, the optimal growth and yield parameters also occurred with band placement.

Effect of treatments on yield components, yield, and N use efficiency in rice. ARS, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Treatment	N rate (kg/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)		Yield (t/ha)				N use efficiency			
				Grain		Straw		Agronomic efficiency (kg grain/kg N)		Apparent recovery (%)	
				IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36
Control (No N)	0	460	420	3.6	3.8	3.8	4.7	-	-	-	-
BC ^a 50% N as basal + 25% N each at 15 and 35 DAT ^b as PU ^c	100	510	435	4.6	5.4	4.6	5.6	10.3	15.8	18.3	22.8
BP ^d of urea solution at 1/3 N at 15 DAT + 2/3 N at 35 DAT	50	600	603	5.1	6.8	6.1	8.3	30.0	59.1	62.1	95.2
BP of urea solution at 1/3 N at 15 DAT + 2/3 N at 35 DAT	100	615	625	5.2	7.1	6.2	8.4	16.3	32.4	35.3	55.9
Point placement of USG ^e at 7 DAT	100	565	550	4.9	6.6	5.2	7.5	13.5	27.5	25.8	42.9
BC 50% N as basal as NCU ^f + 25% N at 15 DAT as NBU ^g + 25% N at 35 DAT as PU	100	555	495	4.8	6.6	5.0	8.0	12.3	27.3	22.5	40.9
LSD (0.05)		12	29	0.3	0.7	0.3	0.9	(Not analyzed statistically)			

^a BC = broadcasting. ^bDAT = days after transplanting. ^cPU = prilled urea. ^dBP = band placement. ^eUSG = urea supergranules. ^fNCU = neem-coated urea. ^gneem-blended urea.